

HBM4EU

science and policy
for a healthy future

HORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

Report on Occupational Studies

Deliverable Report

D8.9

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

Deadline: June 2020

Upload by Coordinator: 27 July 2020

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	22/07/2020
Grant Signatory	Antti Koivula	FIOH	08/07/2020

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Argelia Castano	ISCIII	20/07/2020
Work Package Leader	Ovnair Sepai	DH	15/07/2020
Task leader	Tiina Santonen	FIOH	08/07/2020

Responsible author	Tiina Santonen
Short name institution	FIOH
Co-authors	Simo Porras (FIOH), Susana Viegas (ESTeSL/IPL; ENSP/UNL) Karen S. Galea (IOM) Kate Jones (HSL), Elizabeth Leese (HSL), Sophie Ndaw (INRS), Radia Bousoumah (INRS), Ivo Iavicoli (DPH), Veruscka Leso (DPH), Flavia Ruggieri (ISS), Beatrice Bocca (ISS), Radu Duca (LNS), Lode Godderis (KULeuven), Jelle Verdonck (KULeuven), Katrien Poels (KULeuven), Maria João Silva (INSA), Henriqueta Louro (INSA), Paul Scheepers (RUMC), Maurice van Dael (RUMC), Beata Janasik (NIOM), Wojciech Wasowicz (NIOM), Thomas Göen (IPASUM), Marta Esteban López (ISCIII), Argelia Castaño (ISCIII), Ovnair Sepai (DH)

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 2

Table of contents

Table of contents	2
1 Authors and acknowledgements.....	4
2 List of abbreviations.....	5
3 Abstract/Summary	7
4 Introduction	8
5 Aims of the study	9
6 Methodology	10
6.1 Information materials and ethical permissions	10
6.2 Standard operating procedures.....	11
6.3 Company and workers recruitment	12
6.4 Questionnaires to collect contextual information.....	13
6.5 Samplings	13
6.5.1 Power calculations and proposed sample sizes	15
6.6 Sampling methodology.....	15
6.6.1 Air sampling and hand wipes	15
6.6.2 Blood sampling and processing for biomarkers analyses	16
6.6.3 EBC samplings and exposure biomarkers	16
6.6.4 Urine sample collections and exposure biomarkers.....	17
6.6.5 Quality assurance.....	17
6.7 Laboratory analysis of the samples.....	18
6.7.1 Exposure markers	18
6.7.2 Effect markers	19
6.7.3 Data analyses.....	19
7 Results.....	20
7.1 Characterisation of study population.....	20
7.2 Exposure monitoring	22
7.2.1 Industrial hygiene data	26
7.2.2 PFAS.....	29
7.2.3 Correlations between the different biomarkers	29
8 Discussion and conclusions.....	30
8.1 Main results and responses to policy questions.....	30
8.2 Future publications.....	32
8.3 Self-evaluation of the study.....	33
8.3.1 SWOT Analysis of the study.....	33

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 3

8.3.2	Lessons learned	34
8.4	Overall conclusions	35
9	References	36

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 4

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Tiina Santonen, Simo Porras, FIOH, Finland
 Susana Viegas, ESTeSL/IPL; ENSP/UNL, Portugal
 Karen S. Galea, IOM, UK
 Kate Jones, Elizabeth Leese, HSL, UK
 Sophie Ndaw, Radia Bousoumah, INRS, France
 Radu Duca, LNS, Luxembourg
 Lode Godderis, Jelle Verdonck, Katrien Poels, KULeuven; Belgium
 Ivo Iavicoli, Veruscka Leso, DPH*, Italy
 Flavia Ruggieri, Beatrice Bocca, ISS, Italy
 Maria João Silva, Henriqueta Louro, INSA, Portugal
 Paul Scheepers, Maurice van Dael, RUMC, Netherlands
 Beata Janasik, Wojciech Wasowicz, NIOM, Poland
 Thomas Göen, IPASUM, Germany
 Marta Esteban López, Argelia Castaño, ISCIII, Spain

The following experts have contributed to this study

Henna Veijalainen, Riikka Helenius, Kukka Aimonen, Jouko Remes, FIOH, Finland
 Carina Ladeira, Edna Ribeiro, Ana Sofia Simões Zeferino, Adriano Pereira, ESTeSL, Portugal
 Célia Ventura, Ana Tavares, Bruno Gomes, Catarina Afonso, Hermínia Pinhal, Ana Nogueira, Sílvia Reis Santos, INSA, Portugal
 Sally Spankie, David Holmes IOM, UK
 Luca Fontana DPH, Italy
 Anna Maria Ingelido, ISS, Italy
 Domenico Cavallo, Andrea Cattaneo from University of Insubria;
 Giuseppe De Palma University of Brescia;
 Angela Gambelunghe, University of Perugia;
 Piero Lovreglio, University of Bari;
 Rob Anzion, Radboudumc
 Guillaume Antoine, Mathieu Melczer, Philippe Marsan, Manuella Burgart, Flavien Denis, Ogier Hanser, INRS, France
 Aleksandra Fucik, IMROH

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 5

2 List of abbreviations

AM	Arithmetic Mean
BOELV	Binding Occupational Exposure Limit Value
CI	Confidence Interval
Cr	Chromium
Cr(III)	Trivalent chromium
Cr(VI)	Hexavalent chromium
EBC	Exhaled Breath Condensate
EDTA	Ethylene Diamine Tetraacetic Acid
EEA	European Environment Agency
GFAAS	Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrometry
GM	Geometric Mean
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HT	Haematocrit
IC	Ion Chromatography
ICI	Inter-laboratory Comparison Investigations
ICI/EQUAS	Inter-laboratory Comparison Investigation/ External Quality Assessment Scheme
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma - Mass Spectrometry
ICP-OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry – Optical Emission Spectrometry
LC	Liquid Chromatography
LC-MS/MS Liquid	Chromatography triple quadrupole Mass Spectrometry
LEV	Local Exhaust Ventilation
Mn	Manganese
MN	Micronucleus
Ni	Nickel
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PBL	Peripheral Blood Lymphocytes
PFAS	Perfluorinated Alkylated Substances
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
QA/QC	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
RBC	Red Blood Cell
RMMs	Risk Management Measures

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 6

RPE	Respiratory Protection Equipment
SD	Standard Deviation
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TWA	Time-Weighted Average
UV/Vis	Ultraviolet / Visible Spectrometry

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 7

3 Abstract/Summary

Occupational studies under HBM4EU aim to collect EU-relevant data on work-related exposures to prioritised substances using harmonised methods. Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) was identified as the first subject for a targeted occupational study since, on the one hand there is a clear regulatory need for occupational exposure data and, on the other hand, there is the need to test new, more specific methods for biomonitoring. Cr(VI) is an occupational carcinogen that has been shown to cause lung cancer in humans. Exposure to Cr(VI) may occur for example in welding activities, in Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment activities.

Altogether eight countries volunteered to participate in the occupational study on chromate exposure. During 2018 a harmonised methodology for the collection of biological samples (urine, blood and exhaled breath) and environmental industrial hygiene samples was developed (Santonen et al., 2019). In addition to chromium (Cr) analysis, samples were collected for the analysis of polyfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS), which have been used as mist suppressants in chrome plating, nickel (Ni) and manganese (Mn) (where relevant) and effect biomarkers (metabolomics, genotoxicity and epigenetics markers). Samplings were performed between October 2018 and May 2019. The analysis of the urinary, exhaled breath condensate (EBC) and blood (red blood cell) Cr and serum PFAS were performed by spring 2020, as well as the complementary occupational hygiene samples. The analyses of effect biomarkers started at the same time, but, given that these are time-consuming, not all of them have been finished.

The results suggest that chromium plating sector has the highest exposure levels. Even with several regulatory frameworks in place (REACH and OSH) exposure to Cr(VI) in plating seems to still occur and at higher levels than in the other investigated sectors. HBM data, together with air and dermal monitoring data, helped to identify the role of different exposure routes in the total exposure of Cr(VI) in the occupational settings under investigation. In addition, it shows the complementary information provided by different (bio)markers to assess occupational exposure. The analysis of the data has only begun, and although a more detailed data analysis still needs to be done, the study has already reached its main goals: to provide EU relevant data on Cr(VI) internal exposure in occupational settings and to evaluate the capability and validity of different HBM parameters for the assessment of Cr(VI) exposure.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 8

4 Introduction

The aim of task 8.5 concerning targeted occupational studies is to overcome the knowledge gaps in workplace exposure in different occupations or tasks in comparison to other exposure sources. This means that EU-relevant data on work-related exposures to prioritised substances are collected in critical occupations using harmonised methods and questionnaires. The data were used to estimate the exposure and to evaluate and identify good practices to control the exposure.

Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is an occupational carcinogen that has been shown to cause lung cancer in humans (IARC, 2012). It is also a common cause of occupational asthma, dermatitis, able to induce also reproductive effects. Exposure to Cr(VI) may occur in several activities, i.e. welding, Cr(VI) electroplating and other surface treatment processes. Cr(VI) is currently a subject for regulatory actions both under the European regulation (EC 1907/2006) concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CMD, EC, 2017).

According to REACH legislation all companies using Cr(VI) compounds have to apply for authorisation for their uses. More than 100 authorisations for different uses of chromates have already been requested, some of these covering hundreds of workers (ECHA, 2020). REACH concerns only the use of Cr(VI) for specific purposes. Cr(VI) is formed, together with the less toxic trivalent chromium (Cr(III)), when metals containing Cr, such as stainless steel, are welded. Management of Cr(VI) formed during the welding process is achieved by compliance with occupational exposure limit values (OELs). The recent binding OEL set under EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CMD, EC, 2017) is 0.010 mg/m³ (as 8 h TWA) for a period of 5 years after the date of transposition of the directive; after that period a limit of 0.005 mg/m³ (as 8 h TWA) will be applied. For welding or plasma-cutting processes or similar work processes that generate fumes, there is a derogation, with an OEL value of 0.025 mg/m³ until 5 years after the transposition date and after that period the limit will be 0.005 mg/m³. On the other hand, in France and the Netherlands, an OEL of 1 µg/m³ has been set for Cr(VI) in all uses. These are the most stringent workplace OELs currently available in EU.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 9

5 Aims of the study

The main aim of this study is to provide EU relevant data on Cr(VI) internal exposure and early biological effects in occupational settings. This is to be used as scientific evidence for regulatory risk assessment and decision-making under EU chemical legislation and under occupational safety and health legislation. The second important aim is to evaluate the capability and validity of different HBM parameters for the specific assessment of Cr(VI) exposure. This includes specific biomarkers for Cr(VI) exposure, Cr-RBC and Cr-EBC, as well as biomarkers of early biological effects, ranging from the classic micronucleus assay to epigenetics markers.

In addition, the study aims to provide information on welders' and platers' exposure to other relevant metals, especially to nickel (Ni) and manganese (Mn), and of chrome platers exposure to mist suppressants containing perfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS).

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 10

6 Methodology

The research plan for the chromates study under HBM4EU was published as AD8.2 in December 2017, available at www.hbm4eu.eu. In addition, the study methodology has been published as an open access scientific paper (Santonen et al., 2019) and it can be applied also by other researchers to produce comparative data. Currently, the same methodology is applied already in occupational chromate studies in Luxembourg and in Denmark.

Figure 1 gives an overall visualisation of the whole chromate study and the sample types collected in the study.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the chromate study (Santonen et al., 2019)

6.1 Information materials and ethical permissions

After the publication of the research plan (AD8.2), a Cr(VI) information sheet, information leaflets to the participating companies and to workers, as well as informed consent forms for companies and workers were prepared in collaboration with task 7.5. These were prepared in English and translated for local languages (French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish, German, Dutch and Finnish) by EEA. The Cr(VI) information sheets are available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/> (Additional Deliverable - Cr fact sheets; French, Finnish, German, Italian, Portuguese, Dutch and Polish).

The information leaflets to the participating companies and for the workers as well as the informed consent forms for companies and workers have been published (in English) as appendixes to Deliverable 7.4 (1st material for communication to participants, including informed consent, <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). Informed Consent forms filled by the study participants will be archived for the entire study duration and not less than 5 years.

In order to collect relevant contextual information on possible co-exposures and operating conditions and risk management measures (RMMs) at the workplace questionnaires (company

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 11

questionnaire and worker post-shift questionnaire) for data collection were prepared. Questionnaires have been published in HBM4EU online library (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/>).

Ethics approval for the chromate study was obtained from appropriate ethics boards in each participating country. Table 1 lists the ethical committees and the dates when ethical permissions were granted.

Table 1: Ethical approvals granted for the Cr(VI) study

Country	Ethics committee	Number	Date granted
Belgium	Ethische Commissie Onderzoek UZ/KU Leuven, Belgium	EC No S61449 / BelRegNo. B322201837343	06-09-2018
Finland	Coordinating ethics committee, HUS Joint Authority, Helsinki, Finland	HUS/879/2018	26-03-2018
France	Comité de Protection des Personnes Sud-Ouest	2018-A01096-49	26-09-2018
Italy	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS)	Prot. PRE 122/18 del 15.02.2018	22-03-2018
The Netherlands	Regional Medical Ethical Committee Arnhem-Nijmegen	Dossier no. 2018-4642	03-01-2019
Poland	Bioethical Committee at the Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine	Resolution No 07/2018	30-05-2018
Portugal	Ethical Committee from Lisbon School of Health Technology (ESTeSL)	CE-ESTeSL -N°. 02-2018	10-05-2018
	Ethical Committee for Health (INSA)	CE-INSA Resolution 12/12/2018	12-12-2018
UK	The University of Sheffield Medical School	HSL27	30-08-2018

6.2 Standard operating procedures

To collect comparable data in a harmonised way, great efforts were made to develop standard operating procedures (SOPs) for the collection, handling, sample storage and transfer for each of the biological and industrial hygiene samples covered within the Cr(VI) occupational study. This work started in February 2018 and continued until the end of 2018 since some of the SOPs were identified as requiring some refining and clarification efforts after the first site visits in November 2018.

The developed SOPs aimed to minimise all the factors that may lead to misrepresentation of the results and are designed considering the pre-analytical phase as a part of the laboratory work. No SOPs were produced for the harmonisation of analytical phase since chromium biomonitoring analyses (except EBC-Cr) were subject for HBM4EU quality assurance scheme as further described under Chapter 7.7.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 12

The list of SOPs is given in Table 2 and they have been published in HBM4EU on-line library www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/. In addition to the SOPs specific for the chromate study, the participating countries followed the general HBM4EU sample transfer protocol and SOPs for the shipment of samples when these are sent from one laboratory to another (published in www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/).

Table 2: List of SOPs prepared for the study

SOP No.	Title	Topic / Sampling matrix
1	Standard operating procedure for selection of participants and recruitment, information to the participants, informed consent	Recruitment and consent
2	Standard operating procedure for completion of company and worker questionnaires	Company and worker questionnaires
3	Standard operating procedure for blood sampling, including sample storage and transfer	Blood
4	Standard operating procedure for the collection of exhaled breath condensate samples	EBC
5	Standard operating procedure for urine sampling, including sample storage and transfer	Urine
6	Standard operating procedure for air sampling of inhalable and respirable dust fraction and (hexavalent) chromium	Air
7	Standard operating procedure for obtaining dermal wipe samples	Dermal
8	Procedure for comparing occupational hygiene measurements with exposure estimates generated using exposure models	Contextual exposure determinant information

SOP8 describes a procedure for comparing occupational hygiene measurements with estimates generated using exposure models. This is a “spin-off” study, that will provide useful information especially for REACH authorisation process on the usefulness and validity of modelling methods commonly used in REACH context in chromate applications. Five countries (United Kingdom, Belgium, Finland, Portugal, France) have participated in this part of the study. These results will be reported later combined with the results obtained from a similar exercise conducted within the 2nd occupational study (on diisocyanates and E-waste).

6.3 Company and workers recruitment

The target population included workers undertaking activities resulting in occupational exposure to Cr(VI), e.g. chrome plating, surface treatment by sanding, spraying or painting, and stainless-steel welding. In addition, a control population of workers not involved in these activities was recruited either from the same companies or from other companies not involving these activities but located in the same area.

SOP1 was followed for the recruitment of the companies and workers, i.e. the selection of participants, recruitment, informing participants and obtaining informed consent. Interested companies received an information leaflet, explaining the aims, objectives of the study and what would be expected from them and their workers through their participation. If the company decided to take part in the study an authorised representative completed an employer certificate of agreement to participate. Workers involved in the activities of interest were approached to express their interest in participation. An information leaflet for the workers was distributed and discussed during the first contact with them. Employees completed a worker certificate of informed consent if they decided to participate. The same approach was followed for controls.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 13

6.4 Questionnaires to collect contextual information

Two questionnaires were used to collect relevant contextual information. These have been published in HBM4EU on-line library (www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/). The first questionnaire was self-administered, and required to be completed by a company representative. This questionnaire aimed to collect general information on the company, including details of the tasks performed and, for example, the amount of Cr(VI) used, work procedures and frequency of operations leading to metal exposure, size of the worked parts, and number of involved workers. Some details regarding general training, exposure monitoring, and occupational health and safety practices were also collected.

The second questionnaire was an interviewer-led worker questionnaire to be completed as close as possible to the end of the work shift. Different versions were prepared for workers involved in chrome plating in baths, welders and surface treatment operators. Questions explored characteristics of the specific tasks, possible background exposures from non-workplace sources and habits that may affect Cr exposure or levels of effect biomarkers. Information on the presence of dental and orthopaedic implants, dental fillings and therapies were asked as possible confounding factors. The questionnaire also collected information on the occupational histories, an accurate description of the tasks performed on the day of sampling and details of the RMMs, information and training, personal hygiene practices, as well as the occurrence of abnormal conditions during work. Both questionnaires aimed to support the analyses and interpretation of the biomonitoring results (biomarkers of exposure and effect).

6.5 Samplings

Sampling started in most of the countries in the end of 2018. Total number of biological samples collected in the different countries are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Biological samples collected per country

Country	Urine (exposed workers / controls)	Blood (exposed workers / controls)	EBC (exposed workers / controls)
Belgium	71 ^a / 19	64 / 31	0 / 0
Finland	50 ^b / 26	40 / 25	33 / 26
France	58 ^c / 24	56 / 22	57 / 22
Italy	48 / 0	47 / 31	33 / 25
Poland	52 / 19	52 / 19	-
Portugal	50 / 27	50 / 27	50 ^d / 24
The Netherlands	20 / 12	20 / 12	20 ^e / 11
UK	34 / 0	-	34 / 15
Total	383 / 127	329 / 167	227 / 122

^a 60 end shift samples, ^b 49 end shift samples, ^c 56 end shift samples, ^d 47 end shift samples, ^e 12 pre-shift samples.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 14

In the research plan, target sample numbers for exposed workers were 50 urine and 25 blood/EBC samples per country resulting in total of 400 urine samples from eight countries and 175 blood and EBC samples. UK did not collect blood samples and PL did not collect EBC samples. BE was not able to meet the stipulated deadline for Cr(VI)-analysis in EBC based on the stability test of 6 weeks due to technical problems, so only total Cr levels were analysed in their EBC samples. Although the number of urinary samples remained slightly below the target, the number of blood and EBC samples exceeded the target.

In addition, air and wipe samples were collected in order to estimate the contribution of different exposure routes to the total exposure. Air samples were collected usually outside the respiratory protective equipment (RPE) from the breathing zone of the worker. In the case of welders, the samples were collected underneath the welding visor (inside the RPE). When relevant and feasible, also respirable fraction was collected outside RPE. Pre-shift, during and after shift wipe samples were collected from both the hands. The data were analysed as both hands combined. The aim was to collect these samples from half of the participating workers. As can be seen in table 4, this target was achieved.

Table 4: Industrial hygiene samples collected per country

Country	Air Inhalable (total) Outside RPE		Air Inhalable (total) Inside RPE		Air Respirable (alveolar) Outside RPE		Wipe*
	Total Cr	Cr(VI)	Total Cr	Cr(VI)	Total Cr	Cr(VI)	
Belgium	26	0	2	0	20	0	29
Finland	41	34	10	3	41	34	41
France	4	43	0	7	0	37	50
Italy	0	0	33	33	0	0	33
Poland	50	50	1	1	0	0	-
Portugal	0	14	0	0	14	0	45
The Netherlands	0	20	0	0	0	20	20
UK	18	0	16	0	18	0	34
Total	139	161	62	44	93	91	252

*Number of workers sampled. Each worker provided 2-6 samples each.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 15

6.5.1 Power calculations and proposed sample sizes

Power calculations were made for urinary Cr to identify the sample sizes needed to detect meaningful differences between the workers and controls. Calculations were done by using ClinCalc Sample Size Calculator (Kane, 2018), which determines the minimum number of subjects for adequate study power. Study group design was one study group vs. population, primary endpoint was continuous (means), alpha was 0.05, and power was either 80% or 95%. Geometric Mean (GM) and standard deviation (SD) of a known population were used in calculations. Urinary total Cr was selected for power calculations because there are background data available for the general population. For other matrixes the data are scarce. A problem with existing urinary Cr data is that in most of the published general population studies no SD data are given. To obtain an estimate of the suitable sample size, we selected general population data from the UK (Morton et al., 2014) and Italy (Aprea et al., 2018) as reference populations. In the UK, the GM of the total urinary Cr is 0.76 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ creatinine (0.26 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and GSD 0.55 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ creatinine (0.24 $\mu\text{g/L}$). Sample size calculations made for this study has been published by Santonen et al., (2019). In order to detect an increase of 10% in GM of creatinine adjusted urinary Cr, the required sample size was about 400 (power 80%). For a 20% increase level the respective sample size was about 100 (170 with 95% power). With non-adjusted urinary Cr concentrations, less than 300 samples were needed to detect a 20% increase in GM. The arithmetic mean (AM) and SD of the total urinary Cr data from Italy were 0.317 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine (0.297 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and 0.334 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine (0.251 $\mu\text{g/L}$), respectively. In order to detect an increase of 20% in AM of creatinine adjusted urinary Cr, the required sample size was less than 400 (Table 3). With non-adjusted urinary Cr concentrations, fewer samples were needed to detect a 20% increase in AM. Thus, overall it can be concluded that the sample size is high enough to achieve required power to detect differences between exposed and non-exposed workers.

6.6 Sampling methodology

Sampling methodology has been described in SOPs 3-7. In addition, methodology has been described in the recent publication by Santonen et al., 2019. To guarantee sample traceability, a standardised convention of the sample code assigned to each worker was used as unique identifier for all samples collected. The same coding system was used also for related documents (questionnaires and informed consent form).

6.6.1 Air sampling and hand wipes

As workers may be exposed to Cr(VI) via both inhalation and dermal exposure, it is important to understand the contribution of each route in the total exposure assessed by biomonitoring. Personal air samples were collected for the assessment of inhalation exposure and wipe samples to evaluate skin contamination.

The air sampling procedure has been described in SOP 6. For electroplaters and surface treatment workers, simultaneous sampling of the inhalable and respirable fractions have been performed (CEN, 1993). Sampling of the inhalable dust fraction was performed at a flow rate of 2 L/min with an IOM-sampler containing an IOM-cassette fitted with a pre-weighed 25 mm PVC-filter (GLA-5000). Sampling of the respirable dust fraction was performed using sampling heads such as the Higgins Dewell type or similar cyclone sampling heads, performed at the required flow rate, with these containing a cyclone cassette fitted with a pre-weighed 25 mm PVC-filter (GLA-5000). For welders, alternatively the SKC Mini-sampler could be used with a pre-weighed 13 mm MCE filter at a flow rate of 0.75 L/min. Samples were collected for a representative period of the work shift.

The air samples were analysed firstly gravimetrically for determination of the inhalable / respirable dust fraction. The samples were then analysed for total Cr, Cr(VI) and depending on the activities

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 16

for other metals using OSHA Method ID-125G (OSHA, 2002) and ISO 16740 Method (ISO, 2005) or NIOSH methods 7302 (2014), 7303 (2003) and 7600 (2015).

Some differences in samples collection and analyses occurred between countries due to the equipment availability in each laboratory involved in the study.

The dermal wipe samples were collected using SKC Ghost sampling wipes (or similar lead (Pb) wipes) as these have been demonstrated to be suitable for the collection of wipe samples for metals, including Cr (OSHA, 2002; NIOSH, 2003). A standardised wiping technique was used to collect samples at designed periods during the working shift; these being pre-shift, first break period, lunch and post-shift. In each sampling period, using a separate wipe for each hand, five horizontal and five vertical wipes across the surface of the palm of the hand (including the fingers) was made, followed by a wipe in the clockwise direction. This procedure was then repeated for the dorsal region of the hand, with each finger then being wiped, taking care to wipe in between the fingers. Field blanks were collected and comprised of one wipe handled in the same way as the exposure samples but were not used to wipe a hand. The Ghost wipes were analysed for total Cr using OSHA Method ID125G. Average hand areas were used in subsequent calculations, these being 535 cm² per male hand (total 1070 cm² for both hands) and 445 cm² per female hand (total 890 cm² for both hands) (EPA, 2011).

6.6.2 Blood sampling and processing for biomarkers analyses

Blood sampling methodology has been described in SOP 3. One blood sample was collected from each (exposed or non-exposed) worker, preferentially on the 3rd - 5th day of the working week. In countries that agreed to analyse effect biomarkers four different tubes were collected: two tubes with sodium heparin for micronucleus and Comet assays; one with potassium EDTA or heparin for analysis of Cr in plasma and RBC and PFAS in serum and one with potassium EDTA for epigenetics, oxidative stress and telomere length analyses. The remaining countries collected blood for one potassium EDTA or heparin tube only, except UK that did not perform blood collection. The samples for RBC-Cr analyses were prepared following the method described by Devoy et al. (2016). The haematocrit (HT) values (measured before (HT1) and after the washing steps (HT2)) were measured to indicate RBC loss during washing steps and the final results were corrected for HT2.

6.6.3 EBC samplings and exposure biomarkers

EBC sampling consists in the collection of cooled exhaled breath as a condensate solution, during regular tidal breathing. In this study, for the harmonised collection of EBC, the TurboDECCS was used as a collection device (Medivac, Parma Italy), in all settings. Two EBC samples were collected from occupationally exposed workers; the first one before the start of shift on the first day of the work week and the second one at the end of the shift towards the end of the work week. For the control group only one EBC sample was collected (time not specified). EBC samples were collected by regular, tidal breathing through the mouth via a disposable mouthpiece for 15 min. EBC samples were collected in all countries except in Poland.

As the stability and integrity of Cr species can be dependent on pH, to inhibit the degradation or interconversion of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) the EBC sample were complexed with an EDTA solution immediately after collection and stored refrigerated (not frozen). Since the volume of EBC collected can vary from one individual to another and since there is currently no proposed volume correction marker, the results will be also calculated per volume of collected EBC (in ng/L). Therefore, it was important to register the amount of EBC sample aliquoted to be complexed with the EDTA solution, and to weigh the remainder of the uncomplexed EBC sample upon return to the analysing laboratory.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 17

6.6.4 Urine sample collections and exposure biomarkers

Two spot urine samples were collected from the occupationally exposed workers, the first before the start of the shift at the beginning of the work week, and the second one at the end of the shift towards the end of the work week. In order to avoid any contamination of urine samples, participants were instructed to remove their work clothes and to thoroughly wash their hands before the urine collection.

Urine samples were collected in previously decontaminated containers (pre-washed with 10% of nitric acid solution) to avoid background contamination. In some cases, containers known to be uncontaminated were used. After collection, urine samples were homogenised and aliquoted in pre-labelled tubes and stored at -20°C before shipment to the laboratories. Samples were analysed for total Cr. Urinary creatinine concentrations were measured and Cr results normalised to creatinine. In addition, urinary Ni and Mn levels were analysed in urine samples from welders and Ni in urine samples obtained from workers involved in the use of Ni in metal plating. Urine samples were also used for the analysis for oxidative stress biomarkers (malondialdehyde, hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine) and for metabolomic profiles.

As a general rule, all samples were shipped to the laboratory for performing analyses as soon as possible and during transportation the storage conditions recommended in SOP3 were assured.

6.6.5 Quality assurance

Candidate laboratories for the analysis of samples for Cr and PFAS participated in HBM4EU inter-laboratory comparison investigations (ICI) and external quality assessment schemes (EQUAS) organised under WP9. The proficiency tests included Cr in urine, blood and serum and PFAS in serum. Each laboratory received two samples of each of the control materials, namely biological specimens, containing the parameters at different levels in each of the four rounds. Each control material was tested for stability and homogeneity by the ICI/EQUAS organisers before distribution according to the SOP HBM4EU-SOP-QA-002, available in the online library. For quantitative evaluation, the results from the participating laboratories were rated using the classical z-scores indicators, according to ISO 13528 (ISO, 2015). Those laboratories that were successful in at least two ICI/EQUAS rounds were designated qualified to perform analysis of the human samples in agreement to the HBM4EU Quality Assurance programme criteria (www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library) (Nübler et al. 2020).

Regarding the analysis of Cr in EBC samples, a suitable ICI/EQUAS scheme did not exist. For EBC-Cr, laboratories with previous experience in this technique and/or capability for method development were selected following the protocol developed under WP9 (www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library) (Koch et al. 2019). In addition, a separate interlaboratory comparison was organised for EBC-Cr analyses. Five laboratories participated in interlaboratory comparison (HSL, INRS, FIOH, ISS and KU Leuven). All laboratories used ICP-MS, with three labs using HPLC, one using ion chromatography and one using microLC (no gradient capability). After an initial exploration round, six samples were sent to all laboratories. These were spiked with Cr(VI) over the concentration range 134 - 3360 ng/L (within the expected observed concentrations, based on previous work) and included a blank. Due to a laboratory relocation, KU Leuven were unable to submit satisfactory results. The four reporting laboratories showed an average recovery of 96.6% (range 83.9 - 113.1 %, no concentration dependency observed) and an average variability of 8.2% (range 5.4 - 12.3%, concentration dependent as expected). No reporting laboratory failed to detect a spiked sample and all reported the blank as <LOQ (varied by lab but all <100 ng/L). When spikes of water and EBC were compared (most spikes were prepared in water due to difficulties in collecting sufficient EBC volume), the EBC sample showed better recovery (101.4% cf 87.9%) and less variability (6.8% cf 9.2%), giving confidence that real samples would reflect at least as good recovery and

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 18

variability as in the comparison. All samples collected were analysed by one of the four reporting laboratories; the results from Belgium have been excluded from the data analysis.

6.7 Laboratory analysis of the samples

6.7.1 Exposure markers

Analysis of the blood samples for plasma and RBC Cr was made by local laboratories being successful in the ICI rounds and designated qualified to perform analysis of the human samples in agreement to HBM4EU Quality Assurance program criteria. Also analyses of the industrial hygiene samples were performed by local laboratories listed below. The analytical methods used for these analyses are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Analytical methods used in different laboratories

	Blood (RBC)	Blood (plasma)	Urine	EBC	Air	Wipe
Belgium	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	LC-ICP-MS ^b	ICP-MS	ICP-MS
Finland	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	LC-ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS
France	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	LC-ICP-MS	LC(IC)-UV/Vis	ICP-MS
Italy	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	IC-ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS
Poland	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	_ ^a	ICP-MS	_ ^a
Portugal	GFAAS	GFAAS	GFAAS	LC-ICP-MS ^c	UV-visible	ICP-MS / IC
The Netherlands	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	micro-LC-ICP-MS ^d	ICP-MS / IC	ICP-MS / IC
UK	_ ^a	_ ^a	ICP-MS	micro-LC-ICP-MS	ICP-OES	ICP-OES

^a these samples were not collected. ^b Belgian data not included in data analysis. ^c Analysis carried out in France. ^d Analysis carried out in UK.

Abbreviations: ICP-MS, inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometry; LC, liquid chromatography; IC, ion chromatography; UV/Visible, ultraviolet-visible spectrometry; GFAAS, graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry; ICP-OES, inductively coupled plasma - optical emission spectrometry.

Analysis of the PFAS samples was made by ISS (Italian samples) and IPASUM (samples from other countries) who had been qualified as successful laboratories in the HBM4EU QA/QC program for PFAS analyses. In ISS lab, this was done by using Liquid Chromatography Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and after extraction of plasma samples with acetonitrile. In IPASUM, the PFAS analysis was performed by LC-MS/MS after solid phase extraction.

Also, other metals than Cr, especially nickel (Ni) and/or manganese (Mn) from the samples of welders and those surface treatment workers who are also performing Ni surface treatment were analysed. This was done together with Cr analysis by using ICP-MS methodology. It should be, however, noted that Ni (or Mn) are not included in interlaboratory exercises under HBM4EU and therefore HBM4EU project cannot assure the comparability of these results.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 19

6.7.2 Effect markers

The chromate study includes also collection of the samples for several effect biomarkers analyses. Since in most cases there is no specific funding for these analyses and they are quite time-consuming only a part has been completed until now. Table 6 lists the effect markers that are being analysed in the chromate study and their status. Only micronuclei in reticulocyte and comet analyses have been completed by this far but the data analysis for these markers is still to be done.

Table 6: Effect markers analysed/planned to be analysed in chromate study

Effect marker	Institute performing the analyses	Current status
Reticulocyte MN	FIOH	completed
MN in PBLs	INSA/IMI	on-going
Comet assay in leukocytes	INSA/ESTeSL	completed
Global methylation analysis (and specific epigenetic markers if pertinent),	KU Leuven	on-going
Telomere length in blood. Metabolomics studies (urine)	NIOM	on-going
Oxidative stress biomarkers in urine	INRS	on-going

6.7.3 Data analyses

A data analysis plan was prepared under WP10. This describes the main research questions and principles for the selection of statistical tests to address these research questions. Data analysis plan is published as part of D10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8.

7 Results

7.1 Characterisation of study population

Characteristics of the study population are provided in Figures 2 and 3 and in tables 7-10. As can be seen in table 7, the study included more welders compared to chrome platers or surface treatment workers. Country distribution was pretty even, although somewhat lower numbers of workers were recruited from the Netherlands and UK. Most of the exposed workers were males, whereas control population contained 28% of females (table 8). Welders were significantly younger than other worker groups (table 9).

Figure 2: Numbers and task distribution of studied workers

Figure 3: Country distribution of workers

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 21

Table 7: Country distribution of workers per task

	Finland	Poland	Italy	France	Portugal	Nether-lands	United Kingdom	Belgium	all together
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)					
Chrome platers	20 (26 %)	0 (0 %)	7 (8 %)	21 (26 %)	10 (13 %)	20 (63 %)	18 (37 %)	17 (16 %)	113 (20 %)
Surface treatment	5 (7 %)	1 (1 %)	3 (4 %)	19 (23 %)	37 (48 %)	0 (0 %)	0 (0 %)	26 (24 %)	91 (16 %)
Welders	25 (33 %)	51 (72 %)	38 (46 %)	18 (22 %)	3 (4 %)	0 (0 %)	16 (33 %)	28 (26 %)	179 (31 %)
All exposed workers	50 (66 %)	52 (73 %)	48 (58 %)	58 (71 %)	50 (65 %)	20 (63 %)	34 (69 %)	71 (66 %)	383 (66 %)
Controls	26 (34 %)	19 (27 %)	35 (42 %)	24 (29 %)	27 (35 %)	12 (38 %)	15 (31 %)	37 (34 %)	195 (34 %)

Table 8: Gender distribution of the study subjects

	Chrome plating	Surface treatment workers	Welders	All workers	Controls
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Females	5 (4%)	3 (3%)	1 (1%)	9 (2%)	55 (28%)
Males	108 (96%)	88 (97%)	178 (99%)	374 (98%)	140 (72%)
<i>Fisher's exact test (vs. controls)</i>	<i>p<0.001</i>	<i>p<0.001</i>	<i>p<0.001</i>	<i>p<0.001</i>	-

Table 9: Age distribution of the study subjects (in years)*

	n	Mean	95% CI	Range	Mann-Whitney U (vs. controls)
Chrome platers	110	44	41-46	20-68	<i>p=0.652</i>
Surface treatment workers	87	43	41-45	24-62	<i>p=0.234</i>
Welders	173	40	38-42	20-63	<i>p=0.001</i>
All workers	370	42	41-43	20-68	<i>p=0.019</i>
Controls	183	44	42-45	23-63	-

*Age is not available from 25 subjects.

Table 10: Smoking habit distribution of the study subjects

Cigarette smoking	Chrome plating workers	Surface treatment workers	Welders	All workers	Controls
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Yes	44 (38.9 %)	32 (34.8 %)	57 (31.8 %)	133 (34.6 %)	23 (11.8 %)
No*	68 (60.2 %)	56 (60.9 %)	121 (67.6 %)	245 (63.8 %)	170 (87.2 %)
Not known	1 (0.9 %)	4 (4.3 %)	1 (0.6 %)	6 (1.6 %)	2 (1.0 %)

*Including former smokers.

7.2 Exposure monitoring

The data concerning exposure will be presented at this stage aiming to answer the policy questions defined in the scoping document dedicated to Cr(VI) occupational exposure (HBM4EU, 2018). Additional work is being developed to provide a deeper analysis of all the data obtained in this occupational study. The production of several scientific outputs to be published in open access journals is also planned.

8.2.1 Biomonitoring data

Results from the RBC-Cr analyses are presented in table 11. Both surface treatment workers and chrome platers showed significantly higher RBC-Cr levels when compared to the controls. Highest levels were seen in chrome platers. The welder group did not show elevated RBC-Cr levels when compared to the control group (table 11).

Table 11: RBC Cr (VI) levels (expressed in µg/L) in exposed and control individuals

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating	89	3.48	2.83...4.13	1.97	1.49...2.60	0.38	0.65	3.48	5.10	6.88	7.99
Surface treatment	85	2.04	1.68...2.39	1.30	1.04...1.63	0.38	0.38	1.80	3.41	4.65	4.99
Welding	155	1.04	0.79...1.30	0.46	0.38...0.56	0.09	0.22	0.38	1.07	4.04	5.28
All workers	329	1.96	1.71...2.22	0.89	0.77...1.04	0.14	0.38	0.72	3.53	5.12	5.84
Controls	167	1.50	1.24...1.76	0.69	0.56...0.85	0.09	0.38	0.62	2.69	4.66	5.01

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

Statistics (Mann-Whitney U test):

chrome plating vs. controls p<0.001

surface treatment vs. controls p=0.001

welding vs. controls p=0.011

all workers vs. controls p=0.053

When total urinary Cr levels in exposed workers were compared to the levels measured in controls, all worker groups showed significantly elevated total Cr levels in urine (tables 12 and 13). Also, pre-shift levels were higher when compared to the levels observed in controls. In addition, a statistically significant increase was seen in exposed workers when post-shift urinary Cr levels were compared to the pre-shift levels (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p \leq 0.001$). Both uncorrected (table 12) and creatinine adjusted data (table 13) showed similar results.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 23

Table 12: Urinary total Cr levels (µg/L) in exposed workers (pre-shift and end shift) and controls (pre-shift)

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating											
-pre-shift	113	2.31	1.77...2.93	1.25	1.01...1.55	0.21	0.60	1.28	2.80	5.97	7.33
-end shift	112	2.90	2.26...3.53	1.42	1.10...1.82	0.16	0.57	1.52	3.12	8.64	10.31
Surface treatment											
-pre-shift	91	0.91	0.66...1.16	0.56	0.46...0.68	0.16	0.28	0.51	1.09	1.82	3.03
-end shift	82	1.46	0.98...1.94	0.78	0.60...1.00	0.16	0.37	0.84	1.98	2.89	3.95
Welding											
-pre-shift	179	0.99	0.84...1.14	0.63	0.55...0.74	0.16	0.31	0.70	1.23	2.17	3.11
-end shift	175	1.22	1.02...1.43	0.75	0.64...0.88	0.21	0.37	0.78	1.79	2.65	3.29
All workers											
-pre-shift	383	1.37	1.17...1.58	0.75	0.67...0.84	0.16	0.38	0.77	1.64	3.14	5.16
-end shift	369	1.78	1.53...2.03	0.92	0.81...1.04	0.16	0.41	0.99	2.12	3.77	7.87
Controls	127	0.33	0.27...0.38	0.23	0.19...0.26	0.08	0.14	0.19	0.40	0.70	0.95

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

Statistics (Mann-Whitney U test):

chrome plating (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
chrome plating (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
surface treatment (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
surface treatment (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
welding (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
welding (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
all workers (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001
all workers (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift)	p<0.001

Pre-shift vs. end shift U-Cr levels in exposed workers (Wilcoxon signed-rank test):

chrome plating	p=0.001
surface treatment	p<0.001
welding	p<0.001
all workers	p<0.001

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 24

Table 13: Creatinine-adjusted urinary total Cr levels (expressed as µg/g creatinine) in exposed workers (pre-shift and end shift) and controls (pre-shift) (includes also samples showing high and low creatinine levels)

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating											
-pre-shift	113	1.38	1.10...1.65	0.81	0.66...0.99	0.15	0.39	0.83	1.96	3.25	3.90
-end shift	112	2.14	1.66...2.62	1.15	0.93...1.43	0.20	0.49	1.15	2.76	6.31	7.29
Surface treatment											
-pre-shift	91	0.69	0.53...0.85	0.44	0.36...0.54	0.11	0.24	0.43	0.85	1.65	2.30
-end shift	82	1.26	0.89...1.63	0.72	0.57...0.92	0.13	0.33	0.74	1.53	2.72	3.63
Welding											
-pre-shift	178	0.73	0.61...0.85	0.50	0.44...0.56	0.15	0.28	0.47	0.95	1.58	2.02
-end shift	175	1.10	0.94...1.25	0.73	0.64...0.84	0.22	0.37	0.69	1.46	2.53	3.33
All workers											
-pre-shift	382	0.91	0.80...1.02	0.56	0.50...0.62	0.14	0.28	0.52	1.06	2.09	3.06
-end shift	369	1.45	1.26...1.63	0.84	0.75...0.93	0.21	0.38	0.90	1.71	3.18	5.21
Controls	127	0.34	0.26...0.41	0.22	0.19...0.25	0.08	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.74	1.22

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

Statistics (Mann-Whitney U test):

chrome plating (pre-shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
chrome plating (end shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
surface treatment (pre-shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
surface treatment (end shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
welding (pre-shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
welding (end shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
all workers (pre-shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001
all workers (end shift) vs. control (pre-shift)	p<0.001

Pre-shift vs. end shift U-Cr levels in exposed workers (Wilcoxon signed-rank test):

chrome plating	p=0.001
surface treatment	p<0.001
welding	p<0.001
all workers	p<0.001

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 25

Data on exhaled breath condensate Cr(VI) levels is still incomplete with French and Portuguese data missing. This means that no conclusions on surface treatment workers can be made yet since majority of these samples were from these countries. However, as can be seen from table 14, chrome plating workers showed significantly higher EBC Cr(VI) levels both in pre-shift and post-shift samples when compared to the control workers. In addition, a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) increase was seen when post- shift samples were compared to pre-shift samples. Although welders showed lower EBC Cr(VI) levels when compared to chrome platers, the levels in welders were significantly higher than in controls and a significant increase was seen in post-shift samples when compared to pre-shift samples.

Table 14: EBC hexavalent chromium levels ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in exposed workers (pre-shift and end shift) and controls (pre-shift)*

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating											
-pre-shift	43	0.14	0.07...0.22	0.04	0.02...0.07	0.002	0.004	0.06	0.14	0.42	0.74
-end shift	51	0.39	0.22...0.57	0.09	0.05...0.16	0.004	0.01	0.14	0.45	1.56	2.01
Surface treatment											
-pre-shift	5	<LOQ	x	<LOQ	x	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
-end shift	5	<LOQ	x	<LOQ	x	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
Welding											
-pre-shift	64	0.04	0.02...0.06	0.01	0.01...0.02	0.002	0.004	0.03	0.03	0.11	0.19
-end shift	64	0.12	0.06...0.18	0.03	0.02...0.04	0.002	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.57	0.76
All workers											
-pre-shift	112	0.08	0.05...0.11	0.02	0.01...0.02	0.002	0.004	0.03	0.06	0.22	0.40
-end shift	120	0.23	0.15...0.31	0.04	0.03...0.06	0.002	0.01	0.03	0.18	0.74	1.22
Controls	76	0.01	0.01...0.02	0.01	0.004...0.01	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.03	0.03	0.03

*Excluding results from France and Portugal, which were not available at the time of the reporting

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value; LOQ, limit of quantification.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test, pre-shift vs. end shift:

chrome plating $p < 0.001$

welding $p = 0.008$

all workers $p < 0.001$

Mann-Whitney U test:

chrome plating (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p < 0.001$

chrome plating (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p < 0.001$

welding (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p = 0.003$

welding (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p < 0.001$

all workers (pre-shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p < 0.001$

all workers (end shift) vs. controls (pre-shift) $p < 0.001$

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 26

To date PFAS were analysed in plasma samples from Belgium, Finland and Italy, including samples from chrome plating worker, welders and controls. The data obtained so far indicate partly extreme high exposure of chrome plating workers to several perfluoroalkylsulfonic acids, mainly PFOS.

7.2.1 Industrial hygiene data

In order to estimate the contribution of the different exposure routes to the total exposure several samples were collected and analysed.

Air samples were collected in the breathing zone of the worker (<30 cm from nose-mouth) to reflect the time-weighted average of 8 hours of inhalation exposure (TWA-8h). This method is used to assess compliance with the occupational exposure limit (OEL). Due to the occurrence of chromium in workplace atmosphere, the dust comprised two size fractions that are defined according to the part of the airways where the particles may penetrate (inhalable and respirable fractions). In this report only the most relevant preliminary data – inhalable and respirable Cr(VI) outside RPE and wipe sampling will be presented (tables 15, 16 and 16).

Table 15: Air sampling data (8-h TWA): inhalable hexavalent chromium ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) outside RPE

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating	62	1.13	0.70...1.57	0.34	0.21...0.53	0.03	0.04	0.39	1.64	3.40	5.06
Surface treatment	25	10.78	-1.98...23.54	0.86	0.31...2.38	0.05	0.09	0.41	9.19	24.44	116.94
Welding	74	2.10	0.76...3.43	0.71	0.51...0.99	0.11	0.50	0.85	1.70	3.00	6.56
All workers	161	3.07	1.04...5.11	0.55	0.42...0.73	0.04	0.18	0.53	1.70	5.05	10.41

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

The data obtained from air monitoring (TWA-8h, inhalable Cr(VI), table 15) was compared with the occupational exposure limits (OELs) available in Europe. Even when comparing with the less stringent OEL of $0.025 \text{ mg Cr(VI)}/\text{m}^3$ there were some results exceeding these levels. About 5% of air samples exceeded the current EU binding limit ($10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with 10% exceeding the proposed limit ($5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). On the other hand, 39% of the samples complied with the most stringent limit value ($1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) adopted in EU (Table 16). When comparing calculated P90 levels to these OELs, it can be concluded that P90 levels were below the binding occupational limit value of $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in welding and chrome plating whereas in surface treatment P90 was higher. It should be noted that these air levels have been measured outside the RPE (when workers use RPE). The next steps will be an attempt to understand why these exceedances occurred through the analysis of the contextual information collected with the questionnaires (which would be discussed in the peer-reviewed publications).

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 27

Table 16: Air monitoring data (8h-TWA): inhalable CrVI outside RPE. Number of samples exceeding the OELs in Europe*

	Chrome plating (n=62)	Surface treatment (n=25)	Welding (n=74)	All workers (n=161)
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
>1 (µg/m ³)	19 (31 %)	10 (40 %)	33 (45 %)	62 (39 %)
>5 (µg/m ³)	3 (5 %)	9 (36 %)	4 (5 %)	16 (10 %)
>10 (µg/m ³)	0 (0 %)	5 (20 %)	3 (4 %)	8 (5 %)
>25 (µg/m ³)	0 (0 %)	2 (8 %)	2 (3 %)	4 (3 %)

*The binding occupational limit value (BOELV) set under EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (EU, 2004) is 0.010 mg Cr(VI)/m³ for a period of 5 years after the date of transposition of the directive; after that period a limit of 0.005 mg Cr(VI)/m³ will apply. For welding or plasma-cutting processes or similar work processes that generate fumes, there is a derogation, with an OEL value of 0.025 mg Cr(VI)/m³ until 5 years after the transposition date and after that period the limit will be 0.005 mg Cr(VI)/m³. In France and the Netherlands, an OEL of 1 µg/m³ has been set for Cr(VI) (MinSZW, 2016; ANSES, 2017). These are the most stringent OELs currently set for workplaces in the EU.

Additionally, table 17 shows the data from exposure to respirable size Cr(VI) particles. It should be noted that the number of measurements is lower than available for inhalable particles (table 15). These measurements suggest a higher exposure to respirable particles in welders when compared to other worker groups. On the other hand, overall exposure based on biomonitoring seems to be highest in chrome platers (tables 11-14). However, a further analysis (including data that are currently not yet available), is needed to clarify and understand these differences.

Table 17: Air sampling data (TWA-8h): respirable hexavalent chromium (µg/m³) outside RPE

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating	58	0.41	0.23...0.60	0.09	0.06...0.15	0.01	0.02	0.08	0.44	1.79	2.25
Surface treatment	13	0.04	0.03...0.06	0.04	0.03...0.05	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.10	0.10
Welding	20	2.33	-0.38...5.03	0.18	0.06...0.53	0.02	0.03	0.11	1.16	13.08	22.31
All workers	91	0.78	0.19...1.37	0.09	0.06...0.14	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.38	1.75	2.67

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

Table 18: Wipe sampling data: total chromium, pre-shift, end shift, shift average (without pre-shift samples) (expressed in µg/cm²)*

Groups	n	AM	95% CI	GM	95% CI	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95
Chrome plating											
-pre-shift	94	0.02	0.01...0.02	0.01	0.0004...0.01	0.0003	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.09
-end shift	84	0.24	0.09...0.40	0.06	0.04...0.08	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.22	0.49	0.61
-shift average	94	0.17	0.10...0.24	0.05	0.03...0.07	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.22	0.48	0.72
Surface treatment											
-pre-shift	58	0.01	0.01...0.01	0.005	0.003...0.01	0.0003	0.003	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.04
-end shift	25	1.24	-0.28...2.75	0.06	0.02...0.14	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.08	5.59	14.13
-shift average	58	0.63	-0.01...1.28	0.03	0.02...0.05	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.43	4.83
Welding											
-pre-shift	99	0.02	0.01...0.02	0.01	0.004...0.01	0.0003	0.001	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.06
-end shift	97	0.10	0.08...0.12	0.06	0.05...0.08	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.13	0.21	0.28
-shift average	100	0.10	0.08...0.12	0.07	0.06...0.08	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.14	0.24	0.32
All workers											
-pre-shift	251	0.02	0.01...0.02	0.01	0.005...0.01	0.0003	0.002	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.08
-end shift	206	0.30	0.11...0.49	0.06	0.05...0.07	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.15	0.37	0.58
-shift average	252	0.25	0.10...0.40	0.05	0.04...0.06	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.13	0.31	0.59

*Average of 1-5 wipe samples collected during the work shift (including end shift sample).

Abbreviations: AM, arithmetic mean; CI, confidence interval; GM, geometric mean; P10, 10% percentile value; P25, 25% percentile value; P50, 50% percentile value; P75, 75% percentile value; P90, 90% percentile value; P95, 95% percentile value.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test, pre-shift vs. end shift:

chrome plating p<0.001

surface treatment p<0.001

welding p<0.001

all workers p<0.001

Wilcoxon signed-rank test, pre-shift vs. shift average:

chrome plating p<0.001

surface treatment p<0.001

welding p<0.001

all workers p<0.001

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 29

7.2.2 PFAS

To date PFAS were analysed in plasma samples from Belgium, Finland and Italy, including samples from chrome plating worker, welders and controls. The data obtained so far indicate partly extreme high exposure of chrome plating workers to several perfluoroalkylsulfonic acids, mainly PFOS. Further analysis of the data is on-going.

7.2.3 Correlations between the different biomarkers

It is also of interest to see whether results from the different biomarkers and from different biomarkers and industrial hygiene samples correlate with each other. Therefore, Spearman rank correlation analyses have been performed to test correlations between all the measured parameters. These analyses were done separately for different subgroups of workers (chrome platers, surface treatment workers, welders). According to the first results from these preliminary data analyses, it seems that correlations between different biomarkers (urinary chromium, RBC-Cr(VI) and EBC-Cr(VI) were low or moderate in all worker groups (correlation coefficients below 0.5, calculated for non-adjusted concentrations, results using creatinine adjustment show similar correlations). This may reflect the fact that they all reflect different exposure aspects: EBC is possibly related to very recent exposure whereas RBC reflects longer term exposure during the lifespan of red blood cells. Urinary total chromium, on the other hand, includes exposure to both hexavalent and trivalent chromium and especially in welding, where exposure to trivalent chromium may be significant.

In chrome plating, the strongest correlations were observed between air inhalable Cr(VI) levels outside the RPE and urinary total Cr levels, air respirable total and Cr(VI) levels outside the RPE and urinary total Cr levels (correlation coefficients between 0.700 and 0.787, $p < 0.001$) but also between wipe samples and urinary total Cr (0.790-0.811, $p < 0.001$). In surface treatment workers correlations between industrial hygiene parameters and biomarker levels were poor, which is likely to be related to the frequent use of effective RPE (and possibly to the use of spray booths) among these workers. In welders, the most significant correlation (0.781, $p < 0.001$) was seen between urinary total Cr and respirable Cr(VI) outside RPE (based on a limited number of samples). Strong correlation was also seen between urinary total Cr and inhalable Cr(VI) outside RPE (0.711, $p > 0.001$). Correlations between biomarker levels and inhalable total and hexavalent chromium (outside RPE) levels were lower in welders.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 30

8 Discussion and conclusions

8.1 Main results and responses to policy questions

These preliminary results from the chromate study were analysed aiming to answer the policy questions defined in the scope of HBM4EU:

Question: *What is the level of exposure occupationally relevant to Cr(VI) in the EU population? What are the groups of risk?*

To answer these questions, we need to consider that all of the biomarkers of exposure applied in this study demonstrate that workers from all the occupational settings are considered to have higher exposure to Cr(VI) when compared with control groups. Most of the statistical analyses performed resulted in statistically significant differences between subgroups of workers by industrial sector (Tables 11-14). Based on the biomonitoring data, chrome plating workers were exposed to higher levels than surface treatment workers and welders with urinary post-shift chromium GM (P90): 1.42 (8.64), 0.78 (2.89), and 1.43 (2.69) µg/L for platers, surface treatment workers and welders, respectively. Control levels were 0.23 (0.7) µg/L. Workers showed higher levels also in pre-shift urinary samples when compared to the controls. The same trend was seen also in RBC-Cr and EBC-Cr analyses; i.e. chrome platers had the highest exposure and the welders the lowest. It should be noted that EBC data are still incomplete especially regarding surface treatment workers.

In the industrial hygiene measurements, the 90th percentile of inhalable Cr(VI) levels was below the binding occupational limit value of 5 µg/m³ in welding and chrome plating, whereas in surface treatment the P90 was above the transient BOELV of 10 µg/m³. The lower biomarker values in surface treatment workers, when compared to chrome platers, may reflect the use of RPE.

Question: *Has the regulation under REACH had the favourable impact like a reduction of GM/median concentrations?*

At early stage of development of the data analysis, only some general inferences are made. The chrome plating and surface treatment settings are in the scope of REACH and OSH regulatory frameworks and the welding only in the scope of OSH regulatory framework. HBM data shows the chrome plating to have higher levels than in welding or in surface treatment even though air levels were not higher than in other tasks. Although the chemical form of the chromates; used and the effect of wearing RPE are likely to have an impact on this, available results also suggest that other exposure routes (hand-to-mouth) may also have a role in the total exposure. The contribution of these exposure routes may be only discovered through the use of HBM data. There was evidence of hand contamination, which may result in additional Cr uptake through hand-to-mouth contact (Table 18) and in chrome platers urinary chromium levels showed correlation with hand contamination (wipe sample results). All the occupational settings showed higher values of contamination during and in the end of the shift (with statistical difference) suggested that hands contamination increases during the day.

However, if urinary data from chrome platers is used to back-calculate air levels, P90/P95 U-Cr levels of 8.64 and 10.31 µg/L can be estimated to correspond to air levels of ~2.5-4 µg/m³ and 3-5 µg/m³ using the existing correlations from chrome plating published by Lindberg & Vesterberg, 1983 and Chen et al., 2002 (for approach, see HBM4EU, 2019). These are in line with inhalable Cr(VI) levels measured in this study (P90/P95 levels 3.4 and 5.06 µg/m³), however, these measurements did not take into account the use of RPE and as discussed above some of the exposure seen in biomonitoring is likely to reflect skin exposure.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 31

In order to conclude whether new regulations have already had a favourable impact on hexavalent chromium exposure, further evaluation and comparison to earlier data need to be performed. However, in this study we have collected a rich dataset, which can be used also as a baseline for future interventions applying the same methodology.

Question: *What are the current HBM methods for Cr(VI)? Which are the appropriate biomarkers for Cr(VI)?*

With U-Cr it was possible to distinguish exposed workers from controls and demonstrate an increase over the shift for all sectors, despite the endogenous background and lack of specificity. Correlation between U-Cr and Cr(VI) air levels was seen in chrome platers and welders and between U-Cr and wipe samples in chrome platers.

The biomarkers more specific to Cr(VI) exposures investigated (RBC-Cr(VI) and EBC-Cr) show promising results; both were significantly elevated in workers compared to controls.

Correlations between biomarkers were low, which supports that their toxicokinetics are different. Even though urinary total Cr is an easy method for biomonitoring, in tasks with co-exposure to Cr(III), it might be difficult to distinguish Cr(VI) contribution to the total urinary levels.

Although several data analyses still need to be performed, some overall conclusions are already possible, namely:

- HBM data shows that the chromium plating sector has the highest exposure levels. Even with several regulatory frameworks in place (REACH and OSH) exposure to Cr(VI) in plating seems to still occur and at higher levels than in the other investigated sectors
- HBM data, together with air and dermal monitoring data, helped to identify the role of different exposure routes in the total exposure of Cr(VI) in the occupational settings under investigation.
- The data shows the complementary information provided by different (bio)markers to assess occupational exposure.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 32

8.2 Future publications

Since the full data analysis is still to be completed, more detailed statistical analysis will be reported in a number of peer-reviewed publications. The planned list of scientific publications is given in table 19. These may be revised and expanded upon based on the consortium's further discussions. Considered will be also given to a special issue of a journal as well as spreading publications amongst different journals.

Table 19: List of topics for planned publications

Publication	Responsible partners (first authors)
Overall results: main findings and recommendations for the use of biomonitoring in Cr(VI) exposure and risk assessment	FIOH, RUMC
Exposure per sectors: combining IH (air, hand) data and Cr-U data	ESTeSL, IOM
Usefulness of EBC in Cr(VI) exposure assessment	HSL
Usefulness of RBC/P-Cr measurement in the assessment of Cr(VI) exposure	INRS, DPH
PFAS exposure in chrome plating	IPASUM, ISS
MN (PBL, reticulocytes), oxidative stress and comet assay, methylation, telomer length	INSA, FIOH, KuLeuven, NIOM
Results on metabolomics analyses	NIOM
Modelling study (combining the results from chromate, diisocyanate and E-waste modelling study)	IOM, ESTeSL

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 33

8.3 Self-evaluation of the study

8.3.1 SWOT Analysis of the study

A SWOT analysis was performed to claim attention for the main outputs of this occupational study and to identify the aspects that should be improved in the future occupational studies that are being planned. Therefore, this approach allowed to understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the Cr(VI) study and similar aligned multi-centre occupational studies, which can be applied to other, similar studies.

Table 20: SWOT analysis

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study served as an ‘educational study’ where several lessons were learned concerning the conduction of aligned, multi-centre occupational studies. It allowed collaboration with different WPs of HBM4EU, including those related to effect markers. • The study provides answers to several policy questions defined in the HBM4EU scoping document for Cr(VI). • It provides a unique set-up including multiple countries collecting biomonitoring and industrial hygiene information (complemented with detailed contextual information) on exposure to Cr(VI) using harmonised protocols that can be applied by others research groups in the future. • Higher number of participants and samples collected from eight different countries allows increased statistical power and a more comprehensive data for EU decision making when compared to national studies. • It provides new information on the usefulness of new biomarkers for the monitoring of CrVI exposure. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the detailed worker questionnaires and samplings reduced the effective working time during the sampling day, which may have had in some cases an impact on the results of some measured parameters. • Regardless of SOPs there were some variation in the case of industrial hygiene samplings (e.g. air sampling pumps were not always switched off during the breaks, there were variability in the sample types collected). • LOQs varied in different laboratories, which may have had an impact on the results of e.g. EBC Cr(VI) measurements since the levels in controls and workers were often low. • On the sampling day workers were not always doing work where Cr(VI) exposure was occurring due to the communication challenges with the company or within the company (e.g. they were welding mostly mild steel instead of stainless steel). Because of this, some individual results are not necessarily fully representing the task. Impact of this possible bias needs to be analysed further.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study provides a rich dataset which can be used to evaluated future inventions (pre and post evaluation using same methodology). • The more detailed data analysis that will be will guarantee more definitive answers to policy questions and recommendations for future studies aiming to study occupational exposure to Cr(VI). • All the aspects that need to be improved were already considered and used to improve the SOPs prepared for the 2nd occupational studies. Scientific publications resulting from the deep analysis of the data will also mention those aspects to avoid difficulties in data communication and analysis in future studies. • Study is likely to result in several scientific publications the data produced and future publications will be useful for several stakeholders, from the regulatory field to occupational health services. • Companies that use Cr(VI) in their production processes may use the data to improve their risk management. The data can be used also for authorisation of Cr(VI) uses under REACH. 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main results of the study do not reach all the stakeholders that may use these data to improve their action. • Ensuring that the communication plan is followed and timings of communication to whom and when is consistent across the various countries. • Personnel time conflicts - a great deal of time and effort will be needed for the further data analysis, reporting and communication of this work at a time when the teams are also getting geared up for the 2nd occupational study.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 34

8.3.2 Lessons learned

There were several aspects which were identified that need to be improved in future studies. Many of these have already been considered for the 2nd occupational studies (di-isocyanates and e-waste).

Questionnaires

There is a need to add more details to self-completed company questionnaire, including questions on general ventilation, LEV, use of PPE, and cleaning. Worker questionnaire, on the other hand, should be more tailored and it should be completed as close as possible to the end of the work shift (or post-shift).

Samplings and analytics

Especially EBC samplings during working time reduced the effective working time. If possible, all samplings (excluding pre-shift) should be done as close as possible to the end of the shift (preferably post-shift).

Air sampling pumps were not always switched off during the breaks although this was instructed in SOPs. SOPs and other common instructions should be followed.

The verification of LOQs in each country for all sample matrixes should have been done before the study began in order to assess the potential impact of possible differences and to consider options for limit the impact of these differences.

Communication with the companies

On the sampling day workers were not always doing work where Cr(VI) exposure may occur, e.g. in some cases welders welded mostly black iron instead of stainless steel. This is a common problem in industrial hygiene studies and its risk should be minimised by more accurate communication with the company representatives including foremen.

Data processing and chromium data template

The SOPs did not contain instructions how to process the numerical data including how to calculate the LOQ in a harmonised way, what is the maximum acceptable LOQ for each sample type, how to treat data below LOQ, how to handle creatinine concentrations outside the 'acceptable range', how to correct blood (RBC) data for haematocrit, or how to deal with outliers.

Regardless of the instructions there were variation how the template was filled and how e.g. air concentrations were given, how data below LOQ were coded. Since inserting of free text to the template or merging cells etc was not prevented, different variations of the template were received. This caused extra work when the datasets were combined when the datasets were checked and sent back for correction. In the spreadsheets, data below LOQ and possible outliers should have also been highlighted to ease the data interpretation. Some spreadsheet calculation and additional data columns (e.g. haematocrit value) could be also added. Overall, the data processing should be harmonised before the study begins and proper instructions should be given how to fill in the data template in order to make this a more effective process in future studies. For this purpose, an SOP on data reporting is under preparation for the 2nd occupational study in order to take into account all these aspects.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 35

8.4 Overall conclusions

Overall, even though there are a lot of room for improvement in future studies, this chromate study showed that it is feasible to conduct European occupational studies in a harmonised and concerted way and to provide data on a number of workers that would have been challenging to obtain in a single country. The analysis of the data has only begun, and although a more detailed data analysis still needs to be done, the study has already reached its main goals: to provide EU relevant data on Cr(VI) internal exposure in occupational settings and to evaluate the capability and validity of different HBM parameters for the assessment of Cr(VI) exposure.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 36

9 References

Anses, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety, 2017 (in French). Expertise en vue de la fixation de valeurs limites d'exposition à des agents chimiques en milieu professionnel - Evaluation des indicateurs biologiques d'exposition en vue de la construction de valeurs limites biologiques et la recommandation de valeurs biologiques de référence pour le chrome hexavalent et ses composés. <https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/VLEP2007SA0430Ra.pdf>

Aprea, M.C., Apostoli, P., Bettinelli, M., Lovreglio, P., Negri, S., Perbellini, L., Perico, A., Ricossa, M.C., Salamon, F., Scapellato, M.L., Iavicoli, I., 2018. Urinary levels of metal elements in the non-smoking general population in Italy: SIVR study 2012-2015. *Toxicol. Lett.* 298, 177–185. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2018.07.004>.

CEN, 1993. EN 481, Workplace Atmospheres - Size Fraction Definitions for Measurement of Airborne Particles. European Committee for Standardization. <https://standards.globalspec.com/std/969024/EN%20481>.

Chen Y-L., Guo Y-L., Tsai P-J, Su L-F, 2002, Use of Inhalable Cr+6 Exposures to Characterize Urinary Chromium Concentrations in Plating Industry Workers *J Occup Health.* 44: 46-52

Devoy, J., Gehin, A., Muller, S., Melczer, M., Remy, A., Antoine, G., Sponne, I., 2016. Evaluation of chromium in red blood cells as an indicator of exposure to hexavalent chromium: an in vitro study. *Toxicol. Lett.* 255, 63–70. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2016.05.008>.

EC, 2017. Directive (EU) 2017/2398 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2017 amending Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work.

ECHA, 2020. Adopted opinions and previous consultations on applications for authorisation. <https://echa.europa.eu/applications-for-authorisation-previous-consultations>

EPA, 2011. Exposure factors handbook: 2011 edition. https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2015-09/documents/techoverview_efh-complete.pdf.

EU, 2004 Directive 2004/37/EC - carcinogens or mutagens at work, 2004. <https://osha.europa.eu/en/legislation/directives/directive-2004-37-ec-carcinogens-or-mutagens-at-work>

HBM4EU, 2018. Deliverable Report D 4.2 WP 4 Prioritisation and input to the Annual Work Plan. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>

HBM4EU (2019) Deliverable report D5.5 WP5 Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>

IARC, 2012. Chromium (VI) Compounds, IARC Monographs - Volume 100C, IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans. <https://monographs.iarc.fr/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/mono100C-9.pdf>

ISO, 2005. ISO 16740:2005 standard, Workplace air – Determination of hexavalent chromium in airborne particulate matter – Method by ion chromatography and spectrophotometric measurement using diphenyl carbazide. <https://www.iso.org/standard/30432.html>.

ISO, 2015. ISO 13528/2015 standard, Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison. <https://www.iso.org/standard/56125.html>.

D8.9 – Report on Occupational Studies	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.0
Authors: Tiina Santonen et al.	Page: 37

Kane, S.P., 2018. Sample size calculator. ClinCalc. Updated November 10 2018.
<https://clincalc.com/stats/samplesize.aspx>.

Lindberg E, Vesterberg O (1983), Monitoring exposure to chromic acid in chromeplating by measuring chromium in urine, Scand J Work Environ Health 9:333–40

Ministerie van Sociale Zaken en Werkgelegenheid (2016) Regeling van de Minister van Sociale Zaken en Werkgelegenheid van 18 oktober 2016, 2016-0000222216, tot wijziging van de Arbeidsomstandighedenregeling in verband de wijziging van twee wettelijke grenswaarden in Bijlage XIII (Bisfenol A en Chroom (VI)-verbindingen). Staatscourant 2016, 57792
<https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/stcrt-2016-57792.html>

Morton, J., Tan, E., Leese, E., Cocker, J., 2014. Determination of 61 elements in urine samples collected from a non-occupationally exposed UK adult population. Toxicol. Lett. 231, 179–193.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2014.08.019>.

NIOSH, 2003. NIOSH Method 9102 'Elements on Wipes'. <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/docs/2003-154/pdfs/9102.pdf>

NIOSH, 2014. NIOSH Method 7302 'Elements by ICP (Microwave digestion)'.
<https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/docs/2003-154/pdfs/7302.pdf>

NIOSH, 2015. NIOSH Method 7600 'Chromium, Hexavalent'.
<https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/docs/2014-151/pdfs/methods/7600.pdf>

OSHA, 2002. OSHA Method ID125G 'Metal and metalloid particulates in workplace atmospheres (ICP analysis)'. <https://www.osha.gov/dts/sltc/methods/inorganic/id125g/id125g.pdf>.

Santonen, T., Alimonti, A., Bocca, B., Duca, R.C., Galea, K.S., Godderis, L., Göen, T., Gomes, B., Hanser, O., Iavicoli, I., Janasik, B., Jones, K., Kiilunen, M., Koch, H.M., Leese, E., Leso, V., Louro, H., Ndaw, S., Porras, S.P., Robert, A., Ruggieri, F., Scheepers, P.T.J., Silva, M.J., Viegas, S., Wasowicz, W., Castano, A., Sepai, O., 2019. Setting up a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 10;177:108583. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2019.108583